

MODERN TEACHING TECHNIQUES IN EDUCATION

**Xusanboyeva Saida,
Abdusalilova Farangiz,
Abbosova Shahrizoda,
Islamova Zilola,**

Teacher and students of English Language
University of Science and Technologies, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *Modern Teaching Techniques have been spread all over the world, which is useful and easy for teachers. Modern Teaching Techniques educate children well and make them understand clearly. In this era, there is an increased usage of the internet in educational applications; this could mean that students and teachers will increasingly make use of technology within open and flexible learning systems. Technology plays an important role in enhancing and developing our learning system. Intended outcomes as well as unintended results of using Modern Teaching Techniques for teacher professional development need to be explored. Certain skills and capabilities of using different Modern Teaching Technologies are necessary for students as well as teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare them for the age of Modern Teaching Technology.*

Key words: *Modern Teaching Techniques, Objectives, Classification of Teaching Techniques, Teaching Techniques, Medias, Benefits, Preparation for Modern Age, Business English, communication, Business English teacher, authentic contex.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a process by which the personality of a child is developed. Thus the education of tomorrow should be able to play its role more effectively by making the individual creative, innovative and effective. One teacher would be unable to cater to the various individual differences of all the students. So Kothari Commission Report (1964-66) recommended “The supply of teaching aids to every school is essential for the improvement of quality of teaching. It should indeed bring about an educational revolution in the country.” The innovative teaching methods with the latest teaching technologies helps the students to achieve their excellence in education. “Technology & knowledge would play an important role in value – addition to our core competence of natural and human resources, a must for achieving our vision of 2020 that is of sustained development.”

- Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, 2003, (Former President of India). Modern Teaching Technique is important and most preferred in the technological age. Nowadays, as classes are modified and equipped with Modern teaching aids such as Speakers, Online Streaming Videos, Interactive Whiteboards, Visualizer, Response System, CD's, Projectors, Educational Software etc, it acts as a tool for the teachers to explain the concepts in a more effective and lucid manner. Teachers can teach the students with more depth and efficiency and also clear all their doubts with Modern Teaching Techniques. Teachers must use various types of Modern Teaching Techniques to

connect with the students. This paper deals with the Modern Teaching Techniques that are used in Education. These techniques help to attain the following objectives.

II. OBJECTIVES

Present the material in more interesting and attractive way Guide and help the students in enriching the qualitative material

Make best use of time and coach the students

Provide individualized instruction

Direct the students toward cooperative as well as collaborative learning activities

Prepare the learning material for students, rather teaching in conventional situations

Diagnose the learning of students and help them to overcome their study problems

Classification of Modern Teaching Techniques

Techniques associated with Teaching Method Brain Storming

Micro Teaching Technique Programmed Learning Inquiry-Based Learning

Mind Map Cooperative Learning

Dramatization

Media involved in Modern Teaching Techniques

Audio Aids Visual Aids

Audio-Visual Aids

Interactive Electronic White Board

M-Learning E-Learning

Modern Teaching Techniques:

Among these classifications, some of the Modern Teaching Techniques with the help of advanced technology are frequently adopted in classrooms. We can see them in a detailed manner.

Brain Storming:

It is a group creativity technique that was designed to generate a large number of ideas for the solution of a problem. Problem solving is a process to choose and use the effective and beneficial tool and behaviours among the different potentialities to reach the target. It contains scientific method, critical thinking, taking decision, examining and reflective thinking. This method is used in the process of solving a problem to generalize or to make synthesis. It provides students to face the problems boldly and to deal with it in a scientific approach. It helps students to adopt the view of benefit from others ideas and to help each other.

Micro Teaching Technique:

It is essential to practise the teaching skills in order to become better teachers. A teaching skill is a set of teaching behaviours of the teacher which is especially effective in bringing about desired changes in pupils' behaviour. Allen and Ryan in 1966 identified 20 teaching skills at Stanford University. This list has now increased to 37 teaching skills. These skills can be assessed by means of an observation scales. It is not possible to train all the pupil teachers in all these skills in any training programme because of the constraints of time and funds. Therefore, a set of teaching skills which

cuts across the subject areas has been identified. They have been found to be very useful for every teacher. The set of these skills are Skill of Probing Questions, Skill of Explaining, Skill of Illustrating with Examples, Skill of Reinforcement, Skill of Stimulus Variation, Skill of Classroom Management and Skill of using Blackboard. Often assisted by a facilitator. Inquirers will identify and research issues and questions to develop their knowledge or solutions. The inquiry- based instruction is principally very closely related to the development and practice of thinking skills.

Mind Map: The Cooperative Learning:

It is a successful teaching technique in which small teams, each with students of different levels of ability, use variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject. Each member of a team is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping team mates learning, thus creating the atmosphere of achievement. Students work through the assignment until all the members successfully understand and complete it. Cooperative efforts result in participants striving for mutual benefit for all the group members.

Dramatization:

One of the Modern teaching techniques teaches students how to behave in a situation by living it. Physical environment/ costumes/ accessories are important and they effect the concentration of the students. Students use their own imagination thus improving their creativeness. It provides direct involvement in learning on the part of all students, improves their language usage, communicating/speaking and listening skills and allows for the exploration of solutions. The various types of Dramatizations are Informal drama, Role playing, Formal drama, Puppets, Pantomime and Finger game.

Media involved in Modern Teaching Techniques Audio Aids:

In the recent past these hearing aids like cassettes and recorders were in used in the process of learning of English language. Such teaching aids were effective in improving the phonetics, pronunciation and spoken English of the students.

Visual Aids:

Apart from the traditional visual aids like charts, pictures and models that are still in use in the classrooms, there are other modern visual aids which were in use in the recent years. These aids include the picture slides, motion pictures and the like. The modern times, the development in technology e-book readers which are portable electronic devices are mainly used for reading digital books.

Audio-Visual Aids:

These are being widely adopted and used in many of the educational institutions, which have a separate audio-visual room or lab. By the growth of technology children are showing much interest in computer-based learning like the Power point presentations. It develops team work among the students as they are required to work in teams for such project based learning. In such a Project based learning teacher acts as a facilitator to the taught and this involves the active participation of the student.

Interactive Electronic White Board:

This is a very recent development wherein the whole board acts like a touch screen with students being able to do various manipulations directly on the board itself. Basically the white electronic board is connected to a digital projector which projects the material on the computer onto the board. Then without the need of touching the computer, the students can do mathematical calculations, scrabble solving etc by the use of a stylus provided.

M-Learning:

M-Learning is the technique where learning occurs in multiple contexts, through social and content interactions. M-Learning Technologies are available by using personal electronic devices such as handheld computers, MP3 players, notebooks, mobile phones and tablets. M-learning is more convenient and access at anytime and anywhere.

E-Learning:

Instructional Content or Learning Experiences delivered or enabled by Electronic Technologies (Ong & Wang, 2004). E-Learning Teaching Strategies are E-lecturing, E- discussion, E-monitoring, E-tutorial, E-access to network resources, E-structured group activity, E-informal peer interaction, E-connected education, E-quality learning and simulation.

Benefits:

Students use Modern Teaching Techniques to:

Participation in a media revolution, profoundly affecting the way they think about

Improve the ways of learning in view of learning fashions

Extend the ability and skills applying their learning environment real situation

Working in groups for cooperative and collaborative learning Developing self-learning habits at their own pace and time Learn with the teacher rather than by the teacher

Develop inquiry – learning habits

Use right information at right time/place to achieve right objective

Review and explore qualitative data

Exchange learning experiences and information with others students and teachers living anywhere in the world

Thus, information technologies facilitate students in their learning process through their active participation on one hand and help teachers on the other hand.

Preparation for the age of Modern Teaching Technology

Certain skills and capabilities of using different Modern Teaching Technologies are necessary for students as well as teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare them for the age of Modern Teaching Technology and they are as follows:

Requiring students to use electronic databases in their searches. Encouraging students to use electronic mail to ask questions, and for submitting assignments.

Becoming familiar with the advantages and disadvantages of the technologies and exploring the capabilities of compact-disk read-only memory (CD-ROM), tele/video conferencing, etc.

Surveying students about their familiarity with the Modern Teaching Technologies and asking if they will share their knowledge and skills with the class.

Using a word processor to develop class notes and editing a version to use as students' handouts and a version for overhead transparencies.

Using computer programs for keeping records in large class enrolment lists, test items and so on and having students review and update their own record from time to time.

Using different packages for data analysis.

Encouraging students to include visual elements as part of their projects.

Spending students' time as a multimedia workstation, planning a presentation; assembling projection graphics, video clips, animation and sound and other materials; trying to match particular materials with specific learning objectives; and integration of the materials into a unified presentation. Eliminating and/or minimizing physical problems arising from the use of Modern Teaching Technologies. Using Modern Teaching Technologies, learners are now able to participate in the activities of the learning communities throughout the world. They may learn collaboratively, share information, exchange their learning experiences and work through cooperative activities in virtual learning communities. Modern Teaching Technologies facilitate teaching and learning process in more productive fashion. In a nutshell, Modern Teaching Technologies are restructuring the teaching learning process to meet the International standards. English has become the language of the business world. That is a well-known fact. It is thus natural that there has been a growing demand for Business English teaching. The term Business English is used either for English taught to different business professionals or job-experienced learners or students who are in schools preparing for business career or pre-experienced learners. This paper is interested in teaching Business English to groups of learners - people who are still preparing to enter the professional field of business. However, many of the principles concerning the focus on communication and intercultural communication apply to all groups of Business English learners. As business people use a specific language to get their ideas across, they need some business communication skills. Thus, teaching Business English nowadays is especially about teaching communication in the authentic business context because learners want to be able to communicate in a way which would be appreciated and recognized by their counterparts. It is more than just teaching English, cultural awareness is of growing importance. Because of very specific goals and needs, it is necessary that the instructor is interested in business topics, although he is not expected to be an expert and he needs to carefully select materials and activities. Authenticity is a highly important issue especially with low-experienced learners.

The difference between Business and General English Business English belongs under the more general English for Specific Purposes (ESP).

It has special and unique characteristics which were stated as a general principle of ESP by Tom Hutchinson and Allan Waters as: "Tell me what you need English for and I will tell you the English that you need" (Hutchinson, Waters 8). In

other words, it is an approach to learning a language, based on the need of the learner, on his apparent reasons for learning. It should also be pointed out that Business English is not so easily defined because unlike other varieties of ESP, it is often a mix of specific and general content (Ellis, Johnson 3). There are many situations where the distinction between General and Business English is not so clear. Also, having certain knowledge of General English is a prerequisite to start learning Business English. This does not mean that one needs to be fluent in English to start studying Business English. There are Business English course books which are designed for different levels of knowledge of English. However, the lower the level of knowledge of the language, the more likely it is that the distinction between General and Business English becomes less clear. In General English one learns the basics, the mechanics of grammar, composition and vocabulary. In Business English you build upon what you learned in General English, you focus on business situations which require clarity and logic, presentation styles that are dominant in business communication. One of the most important aspects of the difference between General English and Business English is content. In General English the main focus and topics discussed will concern family, friends and situations that a person generally encounters in his life. In Business English classes the topics will concern the environment of the office, the life within a company and the skills taught and practised will be such which the learner generally needs in his/her job or will most probably need in his/her future career. The context for listening and reading exercises in Business English is different from General English. Also lexis in grammar will use vocabulary and situations from the business context. Business English is also sometimes called English for Business Purposes (Dudley-Evans, St John 55). It can be further divided according to who the learners are into English for General Business Purposes which is taught to pre-experienced learners and English for Specific Business Purposes which is aimed at job-experienced learners. English for General Business Purposes teaches a broad range of English through business settings. English for Specific Business Purposes courses are often taught in one-on-one setting, even though, not exclusively, and they are carefully tailored to very specific needs of the learner often teaching one or two language skills. (Dudley-Evans, St John 56). Mark Ellis and Christine Johnson called the unique characteristics of Business English more specifically as sense of purpose, social aspects and clear communication. In the context of business meetings, telephone calls and discussions, a sense of purpose is regarded as the most important characteristic of exchanges. The successful use of language is considered in terms of a successful outcome of the business event. Thus it is understandable that those who use Business English need to speak the language to achieve more in their jobs. As there is great competition in business, between companies as well as within companies, it follows that performance objectives take priority over educational objectives or language learning for its own sake. Much of language will be transactional, which means getting what you want and persuading others to agree with your choice of the course of action (Ellis, Johnson 7). The social aspects characteristic of Business English takes into consideration the fact that for business people there is a need to contact others whom they do not know or know very

little. Meetings are often short and there is a need for internationally accepted way of doing things, so that people of different mother tongues and cultures can feel comfortable with each other quickly. Thus social contacts are often highly ritualized and language is used in the context of a routine pattern of exchanges. The style and content of social interactions is typified, marked by the desire for building a good mutual relationship but still avoiding being too familiar (Ellis, Johnson 8). There is a need for clear communication because information needs to be communicated with a minimum risk of misunderstanding. Often it is necessary to be brief, for example when using the telephone. In order to be short and save time certain terms came to be which refer to specific concepts people in business are familiar with. Thus, in Business English being clear and concise often go hand-in-hand (Ellis, Johnson 9). From the characteristics provided above it is becoming clear that communication is a key aspect and Business English can be seen as English for communication in a specific context.

The focus on effective communication

There is a demand for business English which appears to be growing because learners are becoming clearer about what they want to use English for. In today's global economy, learners want not only the skills to read, write, listen to and speak English fluently, they also want to be able to communicate in a way which will be recognised and appreciated by their counterparts internationally. That is the consequence of the Communication Age we live in. (1) claim that the term Communication Age does not only refer to transmissions of digitized bytes from one person to another, but it also refers to communication processes among real people. According to Ciortescu, the ultimate key to successful business is communication (221).

Generally, communication can be defined as sending and receiving verbal and non-verbal messages. It is effective when the message is understood and stimulates the expected action. The essence of communication is sharing – providing data, information and insight in an exchange that benefits both you and people with whom you are communicating (Bové, Thill 4). Effective communication in business context means strengthening business relationships between the company and all its stakeholders. That is why accuracy and proper vocabulary usage in English are so important. The primary objective of learning a language is acquiring specific expressions and phrases. In Business English that means learning business-related vocabulary and content which enable students to communicate effectively in relevant business situations (Weberová 5-6). This requires that vocabulary is chosen from authentic materials according to their usefulness. Further, it is vitally important that a classroom environment is created, in which real communication can take place and be practiced. Learners will feel confident and relaxed if the trainer or teacher meets characteristics outlined below. Interaction will also be encouraged by not overcorrecting, by asking too many questions and allowing time to answer the questions (Ellis, Johnson 37).

The question stands out, which communicative events are of most interest and should be addressed in teaching Business English today. Dudley-Evans and St John list the following based on previously conducted research and published materials:

telephoning, socialising, making presentations, taking part in meetings, negotiating, corresponding and reporting. The authors themselves claims that 'socialising' probably is a misleading term (Dudley-Evans, St John 63-64). Socialising should be replaced by talking to clients, visitors, colleagues and foreign managers as Donna lists it (15).

Communicative Language teaching (CLT)

As stated in the previous paragraphs communication is a key issue in learning and teaching Business English. That is why the communicative approach should be taken when teaching English for business purposes. It is an approach which stresses task-based language teaching, project work and cooperative learning. Celce-Murcia et al. list the following features and manifestations of CLT (8):

The goal of language teaching is the ability to communicate

Semantic notions and social functions are as important as linguistic structures

In case that content is focused on Business English or if it is academic it becomes a simultaneous concern

Group and pair work is common, be it a role play, dramatization or other activities to facilitate language use in different social contexts

Materials and activities often consist of authentic tasks and projects using materials not primarily constructed for pedagogical use

The teacher's role is specially to facilitate communication the teacher needs to be able to use the target language fluently and appropriately.

The core principles of CLT include developing the students' confidence, fluency, autonomy in language, making language practice interesting and social; and teaching language skills, content and forms that are useful, relevant and meaningful. (Celce-Murcia et al. 28-29).

Teaching Business English at university or college level calls for adopting Content-Based Instruction, in which content is the driving force of the classroom activities. The chosen topics provide a framework around which language skills, vocabulary and grammar can be developed in parallel. For exam NJple students at the Faculty of Management in Bratislava, Slovakia study the following topics in English classes in their first year of studies: numbers in managerial work, fundamental principles of management, company structure, personnel management, stress management, management styles, cultural aspects of managerial work, business trips abroad, sectors of economy, international trade, banking, negotiating, corporate finance, accounting, stock exchange markets, insurance, types of businesses, setting up a business. The English course thus consists of a sequence of modules spread over the academic year covering topics studied in classes other than English. This provides a good opportunity to practise language and vocabulary which students have encountered or will encounter during their university studies. The course reflects the needs of students in their current situation. Tasks are a component of lessons which are used to reflect real-world uses of language and create interaction

Intercultural communication

Language and communication cannot exist apart from culture. Culture is complex and has different aspects: national, organizational, professional, personal. It is

something that cannot be spotted easily but it is rather what lies underneath. In Business context the need to communicate with others from different cultural backgrounds makes intercultural communication highly important. Such intercultural competence consists of three dimensions: intercultural awareness (cognitive dimension), intercultural sensitivity (affective dimension) and intercultural adroitness (behavioural dimension) (Brtková 47). A key element for the learners of Business English is that they need to be aware of appropriate language as well as behaviour for cultures and situations in which they will function (Ellis, Johnson 35). These may include matters as purpose of meetings, use of negotiation tactics, information structuring and use of politeness strategies in written as well as oral communication. Moreover, not only verbal but also body language differs in cultures. For example, silence as a negotiation technique might be unnatural for Europeans but very natural for Asian cultures (Dudley-Evans, St John 69).

Culture needs to be taken into account in teaching Business English especially because of the role of English as an international language in business. This does not only mean learning about the culture of native English speakers. The term 'International English' has even been used by some (Dudley- Evans, St John 54) referring to English which is used for communication among non-native speakers. Since we live in such global world where many people interact with others from different cultures, we need to be aware of and sensitive to cultural differences.

Teacher as the facilitator of the learning process

According to Hutchinson and Waters the role of the Business English teacher is different from the role of General English teachers in the fact that it will often involve needs analysis, syllabus design, materials writing and adaptation and evaluation. It is also true that the majority of Business English teachers have not been trained for this specific role, that is why they do need to find their way in this new environment they have generally been ill-prepared for (Hutchinson, Waters 157-160). They often find themselves using texts whose content is not very familiar to them, so it may well be that they will feel inadequate, lacking the ability to cope. However, as Ellis and Johnson state, teaching Business English can also be an attractive field to pursue for teachers. There are several reasons for this: first learners of Business English are often highly motivated, disciplined, intelligent and dynamic. Secondly, it is more than just teaching a language because there are highly specific goals and objectives. Thirdly, there is a combination of professional as well as general language skills, which are taught in the context of a varied and fascinating subject matter (Ellis, Johnson 26). The question needs to be asked, what kind of knowledge is required for a teacher of Business English? Of course, it is an advantage if the teacher knows the specialist subject. Generally, a Business English teacher should not be intimidated by the subject as often is the case according to Hutchinson and Waters (Hutchinson, Waters 163) but rather they need to take a positive attitude towards the specialist content of the texts used for teaching. A knowledge of the basic principles in the area of the subject is necessary, so the teacher 'should not become a teacher of the subject matter, but rather an interested student of the subject matter' (Hutchinson, Waters 163). It is the learner who has the

specific content knowledge. There is a danger that a teacher working with pre-experienced learners will feel a necessity to teach the subject, especially in cases when the learners are not yet so familiar with the specialised content, have not had a real-life experience with it. However, that is not the role of the teacher. The Business English teacher is not supposed to be an expert in any particular business area but in language education. Their specific task is to find the needs of the learners and prepare them for successful communication with their partners in business and also in academic environment for being able to study from specialized textbooks of the subject, or following lectures where the specialized subject vocabulary is used.

An important issue for a Business English teacher is a balance of personal skills. Ellis and Johnson name the following (Ellis, Johnson 27):

An outgoing personality, sensitive to the needs of the learner

Being a good negotiator, a skill most needed especially with job-experienced learners

Being curious and interested in all aspects of business

A teacher of Business English needs to be clear about what the job involves. Their confidence is built up gradually but only on condition of being aware of their duties and the fact that the professional development is a continual process which needs a lot of commitment and time.

Materials for teaching and learning Business English

When considering teaching Business English, a key issue is identifying the current language level of the learner and selecting materials and tasks that are appropriate in level, as well as in content. Nowadays there is a wide selection of published materials to be used for Business English classes. It is easier for a teacher to choose from these, as they make all the decisions in terms of syllabus, content and methodology for them. The problem is that publishers try to reach a wider market. For that reason, it may pose a problem to try to address a specific need of a learner or a group of learners. For such needs additional materials are necessary which a teacher must choose from available published materials or other sources and tailor them to the needs of the group of learners.

Generally, there are three types of Business English materials for teaching and learning: framework materials, authentic materials and tailor-made materials. Framework materials allow learners to produce content and context directly applicable to them. They are diagrammatic representations used to generate language. These kinds of supplementary materials are very suitable especially for visual learners. The use of the term authentic materials has been discussed and some oppose that it is not accurate, that there is no intrinsic merit in a so-called authentic text. The text is only authentic in the sense that it is a message from a writer to an assumed reader, who is expected to have certain knowledge and bring it to the text. Thus it has a value only in the context for which it was originally written (Hutchinson, Waters 159). The authors assert that there is no such thing as an authentic text; texts need to be seen from the point of view of being able to contribute to the learning process. However, most authors use the term authentic materials referring to anything that an English native speaker would read,

listen to or use. Authentic materials are texts, videos, audio programs, films or broadcasts which were primarily not designed for use in teaching English as a foreign language. They can still be used and be of great benefit for learners. It is though a challenge for a teacher to choose authentic material which will be suitable for the goal of the class, which will provide a 'real' experience with the environment native speakers encounter. Also, it takes a certain level of creativity, experience and knowledge to exploit such materials to benefit the students. The third type of materials, the tailor-made materials, refers to such materials which have been produced by a teacher to address specific needs of students. Teaching Business English is about teaching communication in the authentic business context. Creating authentic context is especially a challenge in a class with pre-experienced learners, i.e. those who are still students in universities and colleges or commerce schools. Because pre-experienced learners do not usually have the possibility to practise and learn English in the real life situations in business context, a good approach is to employ methods and strategies to help create the authentic business context in the classroom. We believe that can be achieved by a suitable combination of the used materials. Nowadays when information technology has such an impact on us and Internet has become a vital part of our lives it is natural to use the Internet to enrich lessons. The Internet can especially be used to provide learners with authentic and up-to-date materials. Often course books contain information about companies and their activities which were up-to-date in the time when the book was published but now, some years later, this information is not so accurate any more. We can thus, for example, use the Internet to update such information. Also, it can be used for homework assignments, when students have much information available to choose from and can relate to something that is of interest to them. For example, when learning about organizational structures of companies and various job titles, students can look up the structures of companies they are interested in, bring them into the class and then they can be used for pair work to practise the vocabulary related to the topic. Currently there is a high demand for Business English classes. The reason lies in today's demand for knowledge of English because it has become the international language of business. Learners have a clearer idea of what they need the language for. This paper attempts to generally look at issues surrounding teaching Business English today especially to pre-experienced learners. The difference in English for general Purposes and English for Business Purposes is especially in the content. Effective communication is an essential part of teaching Business English and in today's global world we need to approach it with an awareness of cultural differences more than ever before. These aspects of Business English place a requirement on a teacher of Business English. Even though one does not need to be an expert in the field of business to teach Business English, it is necessary that the teacher is interested in the subject and understands the basics. It is even more of a challenge for a teacher of pre-experienced learners who possess knowledge of the subject mostly from textbooks and not so much from real life situations. That is why authenticity has an important role in such classes. Materials are an important tool of creating the authentic context. This does not mean that only authentic materials should be used, even though they play

an important role. The Internet is a good tool which can be used nowadays to bring authentic and up-to-date materials into teaching. English has become the language of the business world. That is a well-known fact. It is thus natural that there has been a growing demand for English teaching. The term English is used either for English taught to different business professionals or job-experienced learners or students who are in schools preparing for business career or pre-experienced learners. This paper is interested in teaching modern English to groups of learners - people who are still preparing to enter the professional field of business. However, many of the principles concerning the focus on communication and intercultural communication apply to all groups of English learners. As business people use a specific language to get their ideas across, they need some business communication skills. Thus, teaching Business English nowadays is especially about teaching communication in the authentic business context because learners want to be able to communicate in a way which would be appreciated and recognized by their counterparts. It is more than just teaching English, cultural awareness is of growing importance. Because of very specific goals and needs, it is necessary that the instructor is interested in business topics, although he is not expected to be an expert and he needs to carefully select materials and activities. Authenticity is a highly important issue especially with low-experienced learners. In this era, there is an increased usage of the internet in educational applications; this could mean that human beings will increasingly make use of technology within open and flexible learning systems. It plays an important role in enhancing and developing our learning system. Intended outcomes as well as results of using modern techniques for teacher professional development need to be explored. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare them for the age of Modern Technology. Learning from the context (English material that come from GB or America) is also one of the best ways to adopt the language. You will have the chance to see real and modern usage of the language. It means that you adopt the language better than just learning them from word lists that are provided. Using them in your speech inLife and in the real cases will Boost the vocabulary. For these reasons, to meet the International standards students use their Language in English speaking countries visiting or making friend from the countries where English is spoken as mother tongue, their communicating skills will improve and their can adopt the foreign words, items, peculiarities that do not exist in their country. The most Essential aspect of learning a language is loving, living in it, using it no a nonstop base, if the person stops using the language that he she learnt for while than they will forget the words or grammar structure that they learn, it means they have to learn the structures and words again from the beginning. According to statistics of Oxford university and findings of Harvard university child is born and uses the language by imitating listening its usage by the adults. So he or she use it as a mother tongue. A child that is Russian but born in America can use the language of America with correct pronunciation and grammar rule. He or she may have a lot of mistakes in Russian or in other language that he uses later on. The place that we are born will and live in childhood will be Golden manuscripts in the brain in mind and pronunciations. For these reasons parents try to give their children to English

schools. However, if it is not used in a family or with the children surrounded by the efficiency will be less accepted. The Cultural peculiarities, tradition concepts are adopted, learned and used when the people are given opportunities to experience them at first hand. The love to books and movies, songs in English are secrets of the success. There are million, billions and unreachable source that we have but we do not use or pay attention to the important effectiveness that they give. For example, the dictionaries, Encyclopedia and recourses that are kept in libraries, music and sons are keys to the success in learning. They should be the ones that are published and created by English speaking countries. So, we can boost the language skills, listen to real life songs, music and words of life overseas. The Songs that we listen to every day will automatically link our tongue to words, word comes form our mind, it works in automatic way in the ways that we even don't pay much attention. The impact of the real or contemporary English is the key to our lives, success and achievement. Love of the culture, traditions and customs will boost success. The nation, people, nature, villages, towns or countries keep their inheritance and inherits to future generation that is the process that is unstoppable or that never ends. Learning the culture its rules, traditions are live styles will open the doors to improvement which can not be changed. As result you can adopt the culture or new paces without any problems. Your view point or knowledge of cultural peculiarities and differences will make you idol person or the person who can survive in each part of the world, if she or she is chosen be sent to overseas. Books give opportunity to students and teachers to visualize 3D models in the real environment, in real time, and at scale. Many people believe that methods and techniques that are widely used in a country such as America and Britain give the chance to adopt the language better and success of students depend on it. What is the current pedagogy in education in the GB and what are the innovative methods employed to support it? There has been a huge change in, for example how reading and literature is taught. Reading, when I was at university was taught mainly through having access to read books and been immersed in a rich culture of text and opportunities for accessing stories, poetry, letters, biographies, instructions and other forms of the written words. The prevalence of social media and the internet as a whole have changed the way people learn languages for the better. Learning materials should be seen as a dynamic part of the learning process and not just something given out to learners. The principles of adult learning should be incorporated into their development and use, so that they are practical, oriented and relevant to the learners' situation and learning needs. A variety of learning materials should be used to encourage learning for knowledge, attitudes and skills. Find a comfortable, peaceful place for quiet study. You need somewhere where you can focus 180 degree. Last but not least, learn English with LOVE.

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